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Message of Chief Advisor

It is my immense pleasure to know that **Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International** is going to publish **Bangladesh Journal of Dental Research & Education**. Publication of Journal is a manifestation of the organization which will benefit the graduate Dental Surgeons in the field of upcoming and contemporary. Dentistry as well as update development of Dental Health; science education & profession. I also reserve my expectation for the continues publication of the Journal.

Finally I wish complete success of the publication of **Bangladesh Journal of Dental Research & Education**.

Prof. Dr. Md. Ashraf Hussain

Message of Chief Patron

It is obviously my pleasure to know that **Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International** is going to publish it's 1st Journal "**Bangladesh Journal of Dental Research & Education**". For the professionals of Dentistry update development on contemporary Dentistry is a part of skillness in daily life practice and in this field "**Bangladesh Journal of Dental Research & Education**" must play an important role.

I wish complete success of the publication of Journal.

Dr. Md. Raquibul Hossain Rumi

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It is my great pleasure to declare that **Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International** as per its commitment has published Journal of Dental Education & Research, 1st official publication of Academy.

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Finally I wish the complete success of regular publication of Journal of Dental Education & Research.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Jahangir Kabir'.

Dr. Md. Jahangir Kabir

President

Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International

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Editorial

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the members of Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International, bestowing upon me the great responsibility as an editor-in-chief, to edit and publish Bangladesh Journal of Dental Research and Education, the official publication of Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International which has successfully obtained ISSN # 2225-9015. I tried with my utmost sincerity to march the academy one step ahead to best of our combined efforts. I feel proud, privileged and happy to carry out such responsibility and obligation entrusted upon me by my fellow members, especially to Dr. Md. Jahangir Kabir, President, Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International. The Journal will be published bi-annually in the month of January and July each year. I would expect to all to support by contributing their dental related scientific articles for continuous publication of this journal. I do appreciate that, all the members both from home and abroad are coming forward and are helping the editorial board for publication of this scientific journal. This will in turn upgrade Dental Education and research in Bangladesh, and become parallel with international arena of competitive Dental Education and Research.

Our main mission is to combine Dental education, research, training and other dental related information. This journal may initially face difficulties in trying to meet the different aspirations and requirements of its readership with their different backgrounds and needs. However, we believe that the gradual change in structure and presentation of the journal in due course of time will fulfill our dream, that the different needs of general practitioners, post graduate students, trainees and relevant auxiliaries can all benefit by this journal.

At this historical and happy moment, it's my privilege to acknowledge the noble contribution of RENATA Pharmaceuticals with the highest honour for their technical and financial support in publishing this journal.

Finally, may I wish you all, wherever you are, a happy new journey in the field of Dental Research and Education in Bangladesh with the publication of '*Bangladesh Journal of Dental Research and Education*'

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Effects of Matrices for Chondrogenesis and Osteogenesis Induced by Bone Morphogenetic Protein-2

T Saito¹, MA A Polan², J Tang³

Abstract

The effect of matrix on the chondrogenesis and osteogenesis induced by bone morphogenetic protein-2 (BMP-2) was examined to investigate the mechanism of hard tissue formation. Two types of membrane filter made with glass fiber, with fiber diameters of 0.6 and 1.0 μ m, were implanted subcutaneously in rats as a carrier of the BMP-2. The BMP-2 induced cartilage formation within the entire area of the membrane filter with fiber diameter of 1.0 μ m two weeks after implantation. Bone formation was induced at the surface of 1.0 μ m fiber diameter membrane, surrounding the cartilage tissue three weeks after implantation. Four weeks after implantation, bone formation was observed to progress from the surface area toward the subsurface area of the membrane filter while cartilage was persistent in the central area of the filter, indicating typical endochondral ossification. On the other hand, neither bone nor cartilage was formed in the membrane filter with 0.6 μ m fiber diameter even three weeks after implantation.

It was suggested that the fiber diameter of the membrane filter regulates cell-migration and vascularization into the membrane filter which triggers the transformation of cartilage to bone. It was also suggested that BMP-carrier is an important factor to control the cascade rate of endochondral ossification induced by BMP.

In this study, we concluded that the microenvironment produced by the BMP-carrier regulates BMP-induced chondrogenesis and osteogenesis.

Introduction

To understand the complex mechanism of hard tissue formation, it is important to classify the factors which are involved in the biological process of hard tissue formation. There are four factors required for hard tissue formation¹. They are: (1) cells, (2) matrices, (3) mineral ions, and (4) regulators. It was proposed the importance of analysis of these four factors and of interaction among each factor for gaining a new knowledge on hard tissue formation.

Among the regulators, bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) has been known to induce chondrogenesis and osteogenesis *in vivo*²⁻⁷. Cloning and sequencing of the

DNA has been shown that BMP is a member of the TGF- β supergene-family⁸. There are different types of BMPs, these are BMP-2 to BMP-15⁹⁻¹¹. Gene-technology has produced recombinant BMP-2, -4, and -7 available, and they are known to induce ectopic and orthotopic bone formation¹²⁻¹⁴.

To induce chondrogenesis and osteogenesis, BMP requires a carrier as it diffuses into the tissue without a carrier¹⁻⁵. Furthermore, it is thought that the BMP-carrier has an important supporter for cell differentiation as well as a drug delivery system.

Since the discovery of BMP by Urist in 1965¹⁵, insoluble bone matrix has conventionally been used as a BMP-carrier for bioassays of purified BMP¹⁻⁵, and BMP has been thought to induce undifferentiated mesenchymal cells to follow a process of endochondral ossification.

To elucidate the effect of BMP-carriers on BMP-induced cell differentiation, this study investigated differences in BMP-induced chondrogenesis and osteogenesis with membrane filter, made with glass fiber, with different fiber diameters used as carriers implanted subcutaneously in rats.

Materials And Methods

Preparation of BMP/Carrier Composites

The membrane filter of unwoven glass fibrils (Advantec, Tokyo) with two fiber diameters, 1.0 and 0.6

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mm (the fiber diameter is the same as exclusive size in the membrane) were cut into rectangular sizes, 10 x 5 x 1 mm (6 mg). Then, 1.1 mg of BMP-2 in 0.05ml of phosphate-buffered saline was absorbed to them (BMP-2/1.0 and BMP-2/0.6).

Implantation of BMP/Carrier Composites

Four-week-old wistar strain male rats (about 60 g body weight) were anesthetized intraperitoneally with pentobarbital sodium (4 mg/100 g body weight). The back skin was shaved, cleaned with 70% alcohol and iodine, and subcutaneous pockets were formed by using surgical knife and blunt instrument. The BMP/carrier composites were implanted with tweezers in the subcutaneous pockets and sutured. The animals were killed with an overdose of ether one, two, three and four weeks after implantation. The implants were removed and subjected to biochemical analysis and histological observation.

Biochemical Analysis

The extracted pellets were lyophilized and stored frozen at -80 °C until analysis. The samples were cut with scissors in a conical tube into fine powders of about 0.1 mm in particle size. An aliquot of sample was shaken with a vortex in 0.2% Nonidet P-40, 10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, pH 7.5 at 4 °C for 24 hours. After centrifugation of the suspension, the ALP activity in the supernatant was measured by the Kind-King phenylphosphate method¹⁶.

A further aliquot of sample was hydrolyzed with 6N hydrochloric acid. The calcium content in the hydrolyzed sample was measured by the orthocresolphthalein complexon method¹⁷.

For determination of type II collagen, the remaining minced pellets were treated with 0.1% pepsin, 0.5 M acetic acid followed by 20 mM dithiothreitol¹⁸, 1 M NaCl, 50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4 including protease inhibitors (50 mM aminocaproic acid, 5 mM benzamidinehydrochloride, 1 mM benzylsulfonylfluoride) at 4 °C. The digests were purified by 0.8 M salt precipitation at acidic pH. The precipitation was solved with 0.5 M acetic acid and used for the assay. Type II collagen was identified and quantified by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays using anti-bovine type II collagen antibody (Life Science, Tokyo) with bovine type II collagen as the standard.

Histological Observation

The extracted pellets were fixed in 10% neutral formalin buffer, demineralized in 10% formic acid, embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 4 μm, and stained

with hematoxylin and eosin for light microscopy observation.

Results

Biochemical Analysis

The dry weight, ALP activity, calcium and type II collagen contents induced were compared between BMP-2/1.0 and BMP-2/0.6, two weeks after implantation (Fig. 1). The BMP-2/1.0 showed higher values in dry weight, ALP activity, calcium and type II collagen contents than the BMP-2/0.6. Particularly, the BMP-2/0.6 showed very low values in ALP activity, calcium and type II collagen contents.

Figure 1. Dry weights (a), alkaline phosphatase activities (b), calcium contents (c), and type II collagen contents (d) of BMP-2/1.0 and BMP-2/0.6 harvested two weeks after implantation. Vertical bars indicate standard deviations (n=3).

Histological Observation

In BMP-2/1.0, one week after implantation, cell migration was observed at only surface area of the membrane filter (Fig. 2a). Two weeks after implantation, cartilage was observed in the filter (Fig. 2b). Most of the volume of the filter was filled with cartilagenous matrix and chondrocyte-like cells. Bone formation surrounding the cartilage was observed on the surface of the membrane three weeks after implantation (Fig. 2c). Bone formation was observed to progress from the surface area toward the subsurface area of the membrane filter while cartilage was persistent in the central area of the filter (Fig. 2d).

Figure 2. Histological observations of BMP-2/1.0 harvested one (a), two (b), three (c) and four (d) weeks after implantation. C: cartilage. B: bone. Original magnification x 100.

On the other hand, neither bone nor cartilage was formed in the membrane filter in BMP-2/0.6 even three weeks after implantation (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Histological observations of BMP-2/0.6 harvested two weeks after implantation. Original magnification x 100.

Discussion

This study showed the effect of BMP-carrier on the processes of osteogenesis and chondrogenesis induced by BMP-2. The biochemical and histological analysis showed cartilage formation in the BMP-2/1.0 two weeks after implantation. Only a small number of undifferentiated mesenchymal cells may be able to invade into the membrane with 0.6 mm diameter of fibers because the mesh structure is tight while a larger number of cells may invade the membrane with a looser mesh structure. Thus, the BMP-2/0.6 induced either bone formation or cartilage formation. Bone formation was observed at the surface of the 1.0mm filter surrounding the cartilage which was induced at the

central area of the membrane filter three weeks after implantation. Moreover, bone formation progressed from the surface area toward the subsurface area of the membrane filter while cartilage was persistent in the central area of the filter four weeks after implantation, showing the slow cascade of endochondral bone formation.

The effect of the cell-substratum on cell differentiation was first described by Reddi and Huggins²³. They implanted decalcified bone powders containing intact BMP with two distinct particle sizes under rat skin, and found that the coarser powder, with particle sizes of 420-850 μ m, induced more bone formation than the finer powder, with particle sizes of 44-74 μ m. This indicated that BMP-induced bone formation depends on the carrier geometry.

The membrane filter with the 1 mm fiber diameter combined with BMP induced endochondral ossification which cartilage is persistent for a long period. We attributed this phenomenon in the filter to the delay of vascularization and blood supply into the carrier. Bassett reported that a low oxygen concentration plays a role in the induction of chondrogenesis, while a high oxygen concentration was necessary to induce bone formation²⁴. We hypothesized that the membrane filter, with its fine solid fibrillar structure, prevents blood vessels from invasion into the membrane in the early stage of implantation with BMP. Therefore, it was suggested that the membrane filter creates a lacking in blood supply and oxygen supply, which is favorable for chondrogenesis. This microenvironment seemed to facilitate the differentiation of immature mesenchymal cells, which had invaded the membrane filter by chemotaxis induced by BMP, into chondrocytes, and sustain cartilage in the membrane filter for a long time.

This study suggested that the local oxygen pressure supplied by invasion of blood vessels into the BMP-carrier is very important for cell-differentiation. It was also indicated that the microenvironment induced by the geometry of matrices on which undifferentiated mesenchymal cells attach is involved in regulating the direction of BMP-derived cell differentiation. Further, this study suggested the possibility of individual induction of bone or cartilage formation utilizing BMP by regulation of the microenvironment surrounding the cells according to the purpose.

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Study On Microbiological Organisms Responsible For Chronic Osteomyelitis Of The Jaw in Bangladesh

AKMS Moral¹, T Begum², AFMS Rahman³
MM Hasan⁴, MM Islam⁵

Abstract

The present cross sectional study consists of 50 patients and was conducted between July 2008 and June 2009 in the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Dhaka Dental College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh. The number of male patients was higher than the female and the age of the patient was mostly found in third and fourth decade. The majority of the lesions were found in the body of the mandible and had resulted from odontogenic infections, post-extraction complication, inadequate removal of necrotic bone, early termination of antibiotic therapy, inappropriate selection of antibiotic, diagnostic failure, trauma and inadequate treatment for fracture. In this study, the most common causes of chronic osteomyelitis of the jaws were directly related to odontogenic infections like infected unhealed socket (60%). The most common pathogenic micro-organism causing chronic osteomyelitis of the jaws was found to be Staphylococcus aureus (82%).

Introduction

Chronic Osteomyelitis is a persistent disease of bone that is characterized by inflammatory processes, including necrosis of mineralized and marrow tissue, suppuration, resumption, sclerosis, and hyperplasia^{1,2}. In contemporary world, the incidence of Osteomyelitis of the jaw has declined because of the wide spread availability of the newer antimicrobial agent, better awareness and better dental health care while we come across a large number of osteomyelitis cases and its causes can be attributed due to inappropriate and indiscriminate use of antibiotic, less awareness about dental and oral hygiene, malnutrition, developing of certain strain of microorganism which are resistant to certain antibiotic. The following factors that also predispose to osteomyelitis of the jaw are virulence of the microorganism, compromised vascular integrity and perfusion in the host bone at the local, regional or systemic level and condition affecting host resistance or defence³. The disease may be acute, subacute or chronic each of which produce a completely different clinical

picture. Chronic Osteomyelitis of the jaw has a variety of clinical appearances and related with various etiologic factors. Therefore the diagnosis is more difficult^{4,5}. Culture and sensitivity, bone and soft tissue biopsy, conventional radiography, specialized radiography, radioisotope bone scanning, laser dopler flowmetry, computerized tomography and magnetic resonance imaging are used in diagnosing chronic Osteomyelitis⁶⁻⁹. Radioisotope, bone scanning, ^{99m}Tc, Methylene diphosphonate reveal strong uptake in the maxilla and mandible¹⁰. Tissue specimen need to be cultured and once soft tissue and bone specimen have been obtained, they must be sent to the microbiological laboratory to identify the causative microorganism¹¹. The clinical presentation of chronic Osteomyelitis include pain, tenderness, swelling, intraoral and extraoral purulent pus discharge present of sequestra and radiographic changes. Typical radiographic change usually do not appear

For several weeks. Therapy for osteomyelitis requires a multidisciplinary approach. A precise microbiological diagnosis, exploration and adequate surgical debridement of necrotic tissue are essential in case of chronic osteomyelitis¹².

The purpose of this study was to evaluate chronic osteomyelitis of the jaw giving more emphasis on identification of the specific microorganism for its definitive antibiotic treatment protocol, which may help in achieving better treatment results and minimize post operative complication.

Results and Observations:

This prospective study was conducted in Dhaka Dental College and Hospital for a period of two years started from July, 2008 to June, 2009. Initially 55 patients were

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Fig. 2: OPG shows the radiopaque sequestra sinus in the mandible

Fig. 3: Post operative photograph

Discussion

The primary cause of chronic osteomyelitis is usually microbiologic and result from an odontogenic infection, post extraction complication, inadequate removal of necrotic bone, early termination of antibiotic therapy, inappropriate selection of antibiotic, diagnostic failure, trauma, inadequate treatment for fracture and irradiation of the mandible.

In this study a total 50 patient were studied and among them the most common causes of chronic osteomyelitis of the jaws were directly related to odontogenic infections like infected unhealed socket (60%), pulpitis (14%), pericoronal infections (10%), periodontal abscess (6%), infected cysts (6%) and gingivitis (2 %). This finding differs with that of SU-Gwan kim et al ¹³. Who found 38.5% odontogenic causes of chronic osteomyelitis. This difference could be attributed to lack of awareness, poverty, illiteracy and possibly maltreatment leading to late presentation of the patient.

Regarding age and sex distribution of the study patients the mean age of the male patients was 37+16.2 years and the females 23.9 +17 years. It was evident that among the male patients highest percentage (50.0%) was in the age group of 35-49 years where as in females patients the highest percentage was in the age group of 0-20 years. Analysis revealed that the mean age of the male patients was higher then the female patients ($P<0.001$) indicating that the proportion of young female patients were higher compared to male patients.

In the study of SU-Gwan-Kim et al ¹³, it was shown that the percentage of chronic osteomyelitis of male patient was 63.3% and female was 36.3% and the highest age group was 50-59 years. Our study however revealed that chronic osteomyelitis patients in Bangladesh are of much younger age group.

Among the study patients chronic suppurative osteomyelitis comprised 94% followed by tuberculous osteomyelitis (2%), actinomycosis osteomyelitis (2%) and chronic sclerosing osteomyelitis (2%). The reason for Chronic suppurative osteomyelitis being the most

common in this study could explained by the fact that the lesion communicated with the exterior skin surface via a sinus.

Culture and sensitivity test revealed 82% staphylococcus aureus, followed by klebsiella (4%), mycobacterium tuberculosis (4%), actinomycosis (4%) and streptococcus viridans (2%). It was observed that (4%) patients had shown no bacterial growth on culture & sensitivity test. This above finding co-related with the observation of SU-Gwan kim at al.¹³

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Oral health condition among tobacco users and non users attending the Outpatient Department of Pioneer Dental College

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Abstract:

This cross sectional comparative study was carried out to compare the oral health condition among 150 tobacco users and non-users in the out patient department of Pioneer Dental College and Hospital, Dhaka. Majority 104 (69.3%) of the respondents were male, among them nearly two thirds were tobacco users and 46(30.7%) were female, majority were tobacco non users. Age distribution showed that majority of the tobacco users were above 26 years; where as majority of the non users were below this age. Tobacco users were found less among more educated respondents. About 33(22.4%) had stained teeth, most of them were tobacco users. Gingival was found more inflamed, tooth was more stained and loose, and tongue was found more coated among tobacco users. Dental caries was present in 83% and majority was from tobacco users. In majority of the non users periodontal pocket was absent, no white spot in buccal mucosa and condition of palate was normal. The study findings showed that oral health condition is better among tobacco non users than among users.

Introduction:

A public health approach to tobacco addiction should include preventing initiation of use, facilitating smoking cessation, and promoting abstinence from all tobacco products by current users. Any product that delivers nicotine confers health risks, yet smoked tobacco clearly confers far greater risks than smokeless tobacco. However, whereas scientists and public health experts acknowledge a gradient of harmfulness, the public may dichotomize products and behaviors as “harmful” or “safe.” Applying the “harmful but safer” concept to the use of smokeless tobacco in comparison with active smoking poses a challenge to health educators and advertisers. Overstatement of harm could prevent smokers from switching to smokeless tobacco.¹

The intense promotion of smokeless tobacco products to young men is clearly intended to foster initiation of use among this population. The legitimacy of harm

reduction is predicted on effective targeting of active smokers and users of smokeless tobacco high in nitrosamine content. Ideally, a product should not be promoted or adopted among either nonusers of tobacco or active smokers capable of quitting. The Swedish experience indicates that *snus* does not serve as a gateway to smoking and appears to have contributed to dramatic declines in smoking as its use increased,² but the response to such products may well differ in the United States. If it is not possible to isolate and market to the group of smokers who could benefit, there may be net harm from these products.

If a harm reduction strategy is adopted, it will require a clear definition of relative health risks associated with low-nitrosamine smokeless tobacco products, perhaps coupled with further limitations on advertising of more dangerous products. A comprehensive strategy is needed from the outset to ensure that the product is marketed solely as a harm reduction tool. The ultimate test of any regulatory approach to these new tobacco products is its impact on public health; thus, careful documentation of patterns and consequences of use is required.

Materials and Methods:

It was a cross-sectional comparative study. The study lasted for a period of three months-April to June 2009. A work schedule has been prepared and followed it accordingly to complete the study in time. The study was conducted in the outpatient department on both male and female patients attending the Pioneer Dental College and Hospital, Dhaka. Due to shortage of time and resources the sample size of this study was limited to 150 respondents. Purposive sampling technique was

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followed to minimize time constrain. All the data were checked and edited after collection. Then data entered into computer, with the help of SPSS for Windows' XP program version 12.0. An analysis plan was developed keeping in view with the objectives of the study.

Result:

The cross sectional comparative study was carried out to compare the oral health condition among tobacco users and non-users in the Pioneer dental college and hospital in Dhaka city.

Total 150 respondents were interviewed and were selected purposively.

The findings of the study have been presented below in tables.

Table: 1. Distribution of the respondents by age group and habit of tobacco

Age group	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
<=25 yrs	7	4.7%	34	22.7%	41	27.3%
26-29 yrs	29	19.3%	9	6.0%	38	25.3%
30-32 yrs	12	8.0%	9	6.0%	21	14.0%
33-38 yrs	12	8.0%	9	6.0%	21	14.0%
=> 39 yrs	15	10.0%	14	9.3%	29	19.3%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

Majority 41(27.3%) of the respondent's age was below 26 years, among them majority 34(22.7%) were tobacco non users. About 38(25%) respondents belonged to 26-29 years group, among them majority were tobacco users. The mean age of the respondents was 28.32 (SD±.365) years.(Table: 1).

Table: 2. Distribution of the respondents by habit of tobacco and sex

Sex of the respondent	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Male	61	40.7%	43	28.7%	104	69.3%
Female	14	9.3%	32	21.3%	46	30.7%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

$\chi^2=0.158$ P=.001

Table 2 shows majority104 (69.3%) were male, among them 61(41%) were from tobacco users. About 46(30.7%) were female, among them majority were

tobacco non users. Chi-square test was done($\chi^2=10.1588$, P=.001) and found highly significant association w

Fig: 1. Distribution of respondents by type of tobacco

Majority 56(75%) used tobacco by smoking, 18(24%) by chewing shada/ jarda, about 1(1.3%) used as ghul (Fig: 1).

Table: 3. Distribution of the respondents by educational status and tobacco habit

Educational status	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Illiterate	9	6.0	0	.0	9	6.0
Upto class 5	3	2.0	6	4.0	9	6.0
Upto class 8	5	3.4	8	5.4	13	8.7
Upto class 10	25	16.8	13	8.7	38	25.5
12 class and above	33	22.1	47	31.5	80	53.7
Total	75	50.0	75	50.0	150	100.0

Distribution of the respondents by educational status and tobacco habit shows that majority 80(54%) were 12 class and above educated, among them majority were non users and rest of the respondents 69(46%) were illiterate to educated up to class x, among them majority were tobacco users.

Chi-square test was done($\chi^2=35.2488$, P<.001) and found highly significant association with tobacco use and education (Table: 3).

Table: 4 Distribution of respondents by condition of gingival

Condition of gingival	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Normal	23	15.3%	29	19.3%	52	34.7%
Inflammation	41	27.3%	21	14.0%	62	41.3%
Elevation	3	2.0%	2	1.3%	5	3.3%
Gingivitis	8	5.3%	23	15.3%	31	20.7%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

The table showed condition of respondent's gingival, majority 62(41%) were inflamed, among them majority were tobacco users. 52(34.7%) gingival was normal, among them majority were non users (Table: 04).

Table: 5. Distribution of respondents by tooth staining

Tooth staining	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	68	45.3%	37	24.7%	105	70.0%
No	7	4.7%	38	25.3%	45	30.0%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

The table showed 105(70%) had staining of tooth, among them majority were in tobacco users (Table: 05).

The distribution by dental caries showed that 125(83%) was present, majority was from tobacco users. 25(17%) there was no caries, majority were in non users (Table: 06).

Table: 6. Distribution of respondents by dental caries

Dental caries	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	66	44.0%	59	39.3%	125	83.3%
No	9	6.0%	16	10.7%	25	16.7%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

Table: 7. Distribution of respondents by periodontal pocket

Periodontal pocket	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	41	27.3%	21	14.0%	62	41.3%
No	34	22.7%	54	36.0%	88	58.7%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

The distribution by periodontal pocket showed that 88(59%) was absent, majority was from tobacco non users 62(41%) had majority were from tobacco users (Table: 07).

Table: 8. Distribution of respondents by white spot in buccal mucosa

White spot in buccal mucosa	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	15	10.0%	5	3.3%	20	13.3%
No	60	40.0%	70	46.7%	130	86.7%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

The distribution by white spot in buccal mucosa showed that 130(87%) was absent, majority was from tobacco non users. 20(13%) had and majority were from tobacco users (Table: 08).

Table: 9. Distribution of respondents by condition of palate

Condition of palate	Habit of tobacco uses				Total	
	Yes		No			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Normal	75	50.0%	74	49.3%	149	99.3%
Ulceration	0	.0%	1	.7%	1	.7%
Total	75	50.0%	75	50.0%	150	100.0%

The distribution by condition of palate showed that 149(99%) was normal, and they were equal from both groups (Table: 09).

Discussion:

This cross sectional comparative study was carried out to compare the oral health condition among tobacco users and non-users in a selected hospital in Dhaka city. Total 150 respondents were interviewed and were selected purposively. Majority 104 (69.3%) of the respondents were male, among them nearly two thirds were tobacco users. About 46(30.7%) were female, majority were tobacco non users. This finding similar with our national statistics³, where tobacco smoking for ladies is not a custom till now, most of the females take smokeless tobacco only. About one thirds respondent's age was below 26 years, majority were tobacco non users. About 38(25%) respondents belonged to 26-29 years group and majorities were tobacco users. About 56(75%) used tobacco by smoking, 18(24%) by chewing shada/ jarda, about 1(1.3%) used as ghul. This finding similar with our national statistics³ Where majority of the tobacco users are smokers. About 62(41%) respondent's gingival were found inflamed, majority were tobacco users. 52(34.7%) gingival was normal, among them majority were non users. These

findings similar with the studies^{7,9,10} More than two third had staining of tooth, among them majority were in tobacco users. Loose teeth was absent in 60% of the respondents, majority was from tobacco non users. About 52% had normal tongue, majority was from tobacco non users, and 47% had coated tongue majority were in tobacco group. These findings similar with the studies.^{7,8} Dental caries was present in 83% and majority was from tobacco users and 17% had no caries majority was in non users. These findings similar with the study result.⁴ About 59% respondents periodontal pocket was absent, majority was from tobacco non users. These findings similar with the findings.^{5,5,6}

In 87% respondents there was no white spot in buccal mucosa, majority was from tobacco non users. The distribution by condition of palate showed that 99% was normal, and they were equal from both groups. Tooth decay was absent in 62%, of the respondents, equal numbers were from tobacco users and non users.

Conclusions:

This cross sectional comparative study was carried out to compare the oral health condition among 150 tobacco users and non-users. About two thirds of the respondents were male majority were tobacco users and rest one third were female, majority were tobacco non users. Age distribution showed that majority of the tobacco users were above 26 years; where as majority of the non users were below this age. Tobacco users were found less among more educated. Among the tobacco users, gingival was found more inflamed, tooth was more stained and loose, and tongue was found more coated. Dental caries was present in majority among the tobacco users. Among the non users, in majority of the cases periodontal pocket was absent, in buccal mucosa white spot was absent and condition of palate was normal.

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Severely curved mandibular molar teeth managed by Nickel titanium K-flex files and balanced force technique

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of Nickel titanium K files in maintaining root canal curvature of severely curved mandibular molar teeth. 15 mandibular first and second molar teeth having the curvature more than 25 degree were involved in this study. Working length measuring X-ray and post operative x-ray after canal preparation by balanced force technique using Ni Ti K files were taken by using special type of X-ray device (Crawford X-ray device). Radiographs were converted into computerized digital image and developed for curvature measurements. Curvatures of the canals were measured by Schneider method (1971). The difference in angle between pre-operative and post operative measurements was treated as straightening of canals. The use of Ni-Ti files resulted showed less straightening that means only 1.8 degree of canal curvature

Keywords: straightening, canal preparation, nickel-titanium files, K-flex files.

Introduction:

Successful endodontics is based upon a treatment triad of access cavity, canal preparation and obturation¹³. Cleansing and shaping (i.e. canal preparation) of the root canal is considered to be the most important phase of the triad and is the key to successful endodontics¹⁵. It removes the necrotic pulp debris from the root canal space and also enhances the three-dimensional obturation of the canal.

It is very much difficult to attain these goals with traditional instruments and instrument techniques especially in curved root canal. When instrumentation on curved root canal files tend to straighten and tendency of instrument to move to outer wall, even if pre curved they can cause zipping, tearing of apex of curved canals and create an elbow coronal to the apical zip.⁹

Insufficient shaping will result in less effective condensation of the material and poor sealing of all pathways of root canal space allows microleakage of tissue exudates and re-infection by micro organisms, which creates an unfavorable biological environment for tissue healing to take place. (Robert.1983)

Enlargement of a curved canal by conventional techniques leads to an hourglass shape with a resulting elbow and a teardrop-shaped foramen for which they coined the phrase “Zip”(Weine *et al.*1975).An elliptical or teardrop foramen transportation.(Schilder . 1974)

After many years of experimentation Roan et al, introduced the “Balanced force” concept of canal preparation in 1985. Several studies have found balanced force to be an effective way to maintain the canal curvature.

The Nitinol nickel- titanium (NiTi) alloy has been introduced as a possible adjunct or replacement for SS alloys in the manufacture of endodontic files and instrument. the greater flexibility possessed by nickel titanium files should allow instrumentation to be completed with less changes to the canal shape when compared with stainless steel files².This article present the ability of Ni Ti instruments in maintaining the curvatures of the severely curved root canals during preparation.

Materials and Methods:

This study was conducted in faculty of Dentistry, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, BSMMU, and partly in the Department of Civil

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Engineering ,BUET, Dhaka. The sample size of this study specimen and specified for preparation with Ni ti files(Dentsply). Preparations of specimen were divided into two- Coronal cavity preparation and radicular cavity preparation.

Coronal cavity preparation:

Access cavity was prepared using accelerated speed contra angle hand piece with adequate cooling arrangement. The roofs of pulp chamber were removed. The pulp chamber content were removed by sharp excavator. The canal orifice was explored by endodontic explorer.

Radicular cavity preparation:

Any residual pulp tissue removed from the root canal with a barbed broach. Then the preparation of specimen were completed into several phase.

1. Phase One:

Working length was established by radiograph. Intra oral radiograph was taken in parallel technique using Crawford film holder. Radiograph were converted into computerized digital image and development for curvature measurements¹¹.

Curvature measurement:

On the working length measuring X-ray, the degrees of curvature were measured by Schneider (1971) method¹⁰. In the image a line was traced tangent to the chamber floor (line f). The intersection of 'f' line with instrument (i) determined point A. On the instrument, 1 mm below A, the point A' was determined. The point at which the canal deviates from this line to begin the canal curvature was marked point C. The point A, A' and C were united determined the line 'a'. Other points were marked on the apical foramen and tip of the instrument after magnifying the image by magnifying glass. The point of apical foramen was named by point 'B' and tip of the instruments were B'. The points B, B' and C were united and formed an angle ' α '. This angle was curvature of root canal. This angle was measured by using special type of survey equipment named 'Total Station' Sokkia, Japan.

2.Phase two:

Now all canals of the tooth were prepared by balanced force technique. After completing the preparation of canals irrigation has done by irrigating solution.

Recapitulation has done in every increased the number of file. During canals preparation every set of files was restricted in preparation maximum five canals³.

3. Phase three:

The root canals were ready for obturation which was done with gutta parcha and zinc oxide eugenol in lateral condensation technique.

4. Phase four:

Post operative x-ray was taken in parallel technique using the same Crawford film holder. Than post operative radiographs were also converted into computerized digital image, developed and measuring utilizing the same principles and equipments as described for the measurements of preoperative canal curvature. The difference in angle found between the pre operative and post operative measurements was defined as the degree of straightening of root canal during instrumentation¹¹.

Result:

The curvature was changed with nickel titanium instrument after biomechanical preparation of canals. The summarized data were then presented in the form of tables and graphs.

1. Root canal curvature before and after preparation:

Table 1: shows that the mean curvature of canal before preparation was 31.6 degrees and changed the curvature into 29.8 degree after biomechanical preparation.

	Curvature(degree)	
	Before preparation	After preparation
Instrument		
Nickel titanium	31.6 ± 5.8	29.8±5.

2. The straightening of root canal following root canal preparation:

Table 2: shows that the straightening of root canal curvature after biomechanical preparation were 1.8 degrees.

	Straightening of root canal curvature (degree)	
	Mean	SD
Instrument		
Nickel titanium	1.8	1.3

3. Instrument fracture during canal preparation:

Table 3: shows that fracture of instrument during root canals preparation about 6.7%.

Instrument	Fracture of instrument	
	Yes	No
Nickel titanium	1(6.7)	14(93.3)

Discussion:

Although successful therapy depends on many factors, one of the most important steps in any root canal treatment is canal preparation⁶. Most of the root canals are curved; whereas endodontic instruments are manufactured from straight metal blanks. This result is uneven force distribution in certain contacts areas and tendency of the instrument to straighten itself inside the root canal⁷.

The advent of strong yet flexible Ni ti endodontic instrument remove of this traditional constrains imposed by more rigid stainless steel instruments also reported that the Ni ti hands files were more effective in maintaining the original path of curved canals².

In this article all severely curved canals were prepared by balanced force technique, because balanced force technique produced significantly less deviation from the centre of the original curved canal (Backmen *et. al.* 1992).

In this study one nickel-titanium file was separated during instrumentation. Thus, clinically, it must be considered that curved canals with small radii may occur, which might increase the risk of separation of nickel titanium instruments due to cyclic fatigue¹¹. As nickel titanium instruments are stressed around curved canals with smaller radius, the instruments exceed their elastic limit and separation may occur. This assumption can be confirmed by the findings reported recently by Jardine and Gulabivala, (2000). But the relation between the radii and effects of instrumentation not evaluated in this study.

Weine FS *et al.* (1988) reported that although several nickel-titanium instruments were fractured the degree of curvature did not affected the instrumentation result (curvature were well maintained).

This study compared the canal curvatures before and after instrumentation. Because the angulation at which the radiograph is taken extremely important¹², custom-made bite blocks were used. This step enabled a comparison between the preoperative and postoperative angles without possible differences in radiographic angulation playing a role.

Conclusion:

Ni ti K files were more effective in maintaining the root canal curvature of severely curved root canals of biomechanical preparation of root, was associated with one instrument fracture.

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MAXILLARY NON-HODGKIN LYMPHOMA- A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Extranodal non-Hodgkin's lymphoma of the maxilla could present as one of the early manifestation of detrimental diseases. Clinically these types of lymphoma can mimic an inflammatory endo- periodontal lesion with symptoms of pain and local discomfort. The greater the delay in diagnosis subsequently worsens the prognosis. A case of maxillary non-Hodgkin's lymphoma with an unusual presentation is discussed.

Keywords: Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, Maxilla, Oral lesions, Extranodal

Introduction

Dental surgeons commonly encounter swellings, which could be developmental, inflammatory or neoplastic in origin. Although neoplastic tumors constitute only a minority of such conditions, a dentist must be aware of the various tumors that could mimic an ordinary swelling. A systematic approach including detailed clinical history, proper clinical examination, and use of laboratory investigation would enable the dental surgeon to point out the differential diagnosis of such lesions. Further appropriate histopathological studies would help in arriving at a proper clinical diagnosis. Malignant lymphomas constitute a group of neoplastic, proliferative process of the lymphocytes and or histiocytes in any of their developmental stages. A complete medical history and histopathological examination is required for diagnosis and staging. This case report describes such a case of primary non-Hodgkin's lymphoma involving facial structures.

Case Report

Mrs. Rafeza khatun 35 years female reported to the department of Oral and Maxillofacial surgery on 7th

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February 2007 with the complaints of swelling over confined to her left upper gingiva and gradually involve the left side of upper face especially on left molar area. The local dental surgeon did periodontal treatment diagnosing calculus induced gingivitis. She gave no significant past medical history. She gave no history of cough, chest pain or hemoptysis. On examination there is diffuse swelling over the buccal gingiva extending up to the zygomatic buttress (Fig. 1). On extra oral examination, palpation revealed a diffuse swelling that was non tender and firm on palpation. The swelling was not fixed to underlying structures and skin over the swelling was normal and freely movable. On intra oral examination there is a diffuse reddish swelling over the left upper jaw mimicking gingivitis (Fig. 3). Anteriorly the swelling extends from the buccal gingiva of the left upper premolar area to second molar area and from free gingiva to zygomatic buttress above downwards. On radiography the left maxillary sinus was hazy and periodontal widening was seen (Fig. 4). CT scan of face shows soft tissue mass overlying the left maxillary antrum with underlying bony erosion suggestive of lymphoma (Fig. 2). On histopathology shows tissue infiltrated with lymphoid cells. The cells are intermediate in size and have convoluted nuclei with scanty cytoplasm. The cells are infiltrating in between the skeletal muscle suggestive malignant non- Hodgkin lymphoma intermediate grade (according to the international working formulation). Patient was referred to the department of oncology for further management. They advised her for combination of six cycle of chemotherapy with Endoxen, Doxorubicin and Vincristin and Radiotherapy of cobalt 60 of 4000 cGy for 26 days. Patient was given follow up at a scheduled basis. Four years follow up shows no sign of tumor recurrence both on clinical and radiological examination (Fig. 5, 6).

Figure:1 During diagnosis

Figure:2 CT scan shows left maxillary sinus involvement

Figure:3 Gingival Swelling at diagnosis

Figure:4 PNS showing hazzy sinus

Figure:5 Post treatment PNS X-ray

Figure:6 Post treatment photograph

Discussion:

Lymphoma is second only to squamous cell carcinoma in the frequency of malignant neoplasia involving the tissues of head and neck region, which usually affects the lymph nodes. Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas are a group of highly diverse malignancies and have great tendency to affect organs and tissues that do not ordinarily contain lymphoid cells. Almost 20-30% of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas arise from extra-nodal sites.

The head and neck is the second most common region for the extra-nodal lymphoma, the first being gastrointestinal tract. Among various head and neck sites, Waldeyer's ring, which is the area encompassed by the nasopharynx, tonsil, and base of the tongue, is the most often involved by malignant lymphoma. The nose, paranasal sinuses, orbit(s), and salivary glands are the other sites affected in head and neck region.

Involvement of the oral cavity is not common. The maxilla is affected more commonly than the mandible. Eisenbud and Slootweg found 70% of lesions in maxilla, the most common site being the palate and gingival¹. Freeman² estimates that intra-oral presentations represent 2.6% of all extra nodular NHL and Fukuda³ quotes a figure of 5%. Only 26 cases of the non-Hodgkin's lymphoma of the cheek have been mentioned in English literature. The incidence of the carcinoma involving the buccal mucosa or cheek is very high but non-Hodgkin's lymphoma of buccal mucosa is rare. There has been only one report of NHL occurring in cheek from India. The present case is the first reported case of non hodgkins lymphoma involving upper gingiva and cheek in Bangladesh. NHL usually affects adults between the ages of 40-80 years⁴. The age of this reported case is 35 years.

There are no characteristic clinical features of lymphoma of the oral region. The presenting signs and symptoms are secondary to the lesion. They occur as local bone swelling, tooth mobility, painless inflammation of the mucosa with or without ulcerations, and rarely facial or dental pain. Additional observations include trismus, otalgia, gingival ulceration, sinusitis, or cervical lymphadenopathy^{5,6}. In our case, the patient was aware of the slow growing swelling that was not painful and the skin over the area was normal. Specific and evident radiological signs of bone involvement may be absent in 10-20% of cases. The radiographic findings usually are those of periapical inflammatory processes or osteitis. Diffuse trabecular honeycomb and or dental rhizolytic images are occasionally observed. Those may be the images of cortical destruction and invasion of the maxillary sinus. The reported patient presented with the slow growing gingival swelling only and radiographic evidence of bone loss. There is reversal of the incidence of NHL among young HIV positive patients⁷. HIV patients are 60 times at risk than the general population and around 3% of HIV infected people develop lymphomas. The reported patient is non HIV and did not show any recurrence in 4 years of time. Differential diagnosis includes infectious process such as systemic or deep mycosis, dento-alveolar abscess, dental infections; neoplastic process, wherein very rapid growth is a feature of sarcomas and lymphoproliferative disorders, Wegener's granulomas, and midline lethal granulomas most commonly squamous cell carcinomas and benign tumors like fibromas and lipoma; metastatic tumors. The patient was treated with combination of chemotherapy and radio therapy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, though the NHL involving the oral region is uncommon, it should always be considered in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant lesions in this region, because the treatment and prognosis of these conditions is quite different. Even though a dentist does not treat malignant lymphomas, he/she may be the first to diagnose the lesion. Thus dental surgeons indirectly form a part of the team that treats lymphomas. Moreover, a thorough understanding of the disease process will enable the dental surgeon to refer the patient to the proper sub speciality specially to the maxillofacial surgeon.

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A multi-disciplinary approach for the management of a traumatized tooth with complicated crown-root fracture: A case report

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Abstract:

Complicated crown-root fractures are rare and often need Complex treatment planning. Forced eruption offers a method of treatment of teeth fractured close to the alveolar crest. The present article describes a clinical case of crown-root fracture, with invasion of the biological width, in an esthetic area, where is not possible to carry out the conventional treatment. The fracture line involved the 2/3 rd of the crown, compromising the pulp and extended subgingivally on the palatal aspect invading the biological width. The procedure used to manage this case included endodontic treatment of residual tooth, orthodontic extrusion to move the fracture line above the alveolar bone. Finally the tooth was restored prosthodontically. This case report demonstrates the importance of establishing a multidisciplinary approach for a successful dental trauma management.

Introduction

Seeing children grow from small toddlers into adolescents is an incredible experience for parents. Throughout this youthful and energetic period children are constantly subjected to new experiences and adventures that help them to develop their survival instincts.¹

Trauma with accompanying fracture of a permanent incisor is a tragic experience for the young children and

creates the psychological impact on both the parents and children. If the injury involves the loss of extensive tooth structure, it alerts the child's appearance and makes him the target for teasing ridicule by other children.²

Simultaneous with the growing up process, they also are more prone to accidents especially accidental injuries to the oro-facial region, in particular dental trauma³. Commonly reported causes for dental related injuries are fall^{4,5} especially from a bicycle^{6,7}, contact sports^{5,7} and motor vehicle accidents⁵. Boys are more prone to dental traumas than girls⁶⁻⁸ and the most frequently affected teeth are the maxillary incisors^{4,6-8}, especially the maxillary central incisors⁶⁻⁷. Children between the ages of 8 to 11 years old are generally reported to be affected^{4,8}. Increased overjet more than 4 mm and incomplete lip closure are said to be some of the common predisposing factors for dental trauma⁹⁻¹¹. Uncomplicated crown fractures appeared to be the most frequently reported dental trauma^{8,12} compared to other forms of dental injuries¹³.

Following trauma four treatment possibilities exist: tooth removal, surgical crown lengthening, surgical intra-alveolar transplantation or orthodontic extrusion. Extraction seems to be the easiest choice, yet it requires prosthetic treatment or implant therapy. Surgical crown lengthening can be successfully used in the posterior region, where the aesthetics is not a major concern¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The surgical approach requires osseous and gingival contouring which also affects adjacent teeth. It usually lowers gingival papillas, exposes the cemento-enamel junction, causes hypersensitivity and produces compromised aesthetics¹⁶⁻²⁰. In a 1988 report,

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Kahnberg¹⁹, described a simple surgical technique involving intra-alveolar transplantation. A carefully extruded root, stabilized by interdental suturing and surgical dressing, required endodontic therapy and a porcelain crown. A highly satisfactory alternative to the surgical approach is the controlled orthodontic extrusion of the fractured root. The method is also called forced eruption, orthodontic eruption, vertical extrusion or assisted eruption¹⁷. First reported by Heithersay¹⁵ and Ingber¹⁶, controlled orthodontic extrusion is considered the easiest orthodontic tooth movement that can produce excellent results with a good prognosis and a low risk of relapse. Although highly advantageous, the technique is rarely used; the possible reasons may include the fear of first time approach, a false belief that the procedure is inherently complex, little knowledge in this field and some emphasis on specialist orthodontic aspects involved.

The vertical tooth movement can be obtained with removable or fixed orthodontic appliances, the former using mostly elastic bands or magnets^{14 20-24}, and fixed appliances and many modifications thereof referred to when the tooth is extruded mostly applying a fabricated resinbased crown with a bonded orthodontic bracket^{15-18,21,22,25-31}. There are also some reports on non-aesthetic solutions, such as a hook cemented in the root canal and connected with the interdental bar or orthodontic wire^{17,21,25,28,32}. The lingual orthodontic technique was also proposed for exposing sound tooth structures with excellent aesthetic results¹⁸.

Case Report:

The patient, Md. Monir of 15 years of age came from Sonargoan to the dept. of conservative dentistry and endodontics of BSMMU on 24th October 2005. He gave a history of trauma of tube-well an upper anterior segment, mobility of upper right central incisor. He also gave a history of pain during movement of mobile fragment. Clinical and radiological examination revealed an oblique crown-root fracture in UR1 (11) fracture involving enamel, dentin, cementum and exposing the pulp.

Fracture labially above the gingival margin but palatally it was below the gingival margin and near to the alveolar crest. (Fig-1)

Fig 1: picture showing the oblique crown root

A definitive treatment plan was made as follows- removal of fracture fragment under local anesthesia followed by endodontic therapy of tooth. After this, orthodontic extrusion to move the fracture line 3 mm above the crest was planned to regain the lost biological width. Under local anesthesia loose Coronal segment was removed and endodontic treatment was performed on residual root segment. The canal was obturated using lateral condensation gutta percha technique. (Fig-2)

Fig-2: Radiographic view after obturation of root canal

Then a ready-made post was cemented on root canal by removing gutta-percha by peso reamer from the root canal. The orthodontic bracket was placed on the UL1, UR2 & UR3 by light cure GI. (Fig-3)

Fig-3: Image showing post cementation and placement orthodontic bracket

Then an arch wire (0.16-0.22mm) was placed on the bracket slot and ligated with ligature wire (0.0016).

The elastic band (thread) was ligated with post and arch wire, asked the patient to come after 3 weeks. After three weeks change elastic thread.

When I was obtained the desired movement (3mm) then stabilized the tooth in position for 8 weeks by ligating the post to arch wire with the help of passive ligature wire. (Fig-4a,b)

Fig-4a,b: Radiograph & image showing extrusion of fracture tooth.

After stabilization, a light cure composite filling was done around the post and crown cut was given for porcelain jacket crown.(Fig-5a,b)

Fig 5a,b: image showing composite build up and crown cut

Fixed the jacket crown on the tooth with glass ionomer luting cement.(Fig-6a,b)

Fig 6a,b: radiograph and image showing cementation of crown.

Discussion

Dental traumas due to crown-root fracture are rarely seen when compared to crown fractures^{12, 13}. It is even rare to see a complicated crown-root fracture. Complicated crown-root involves tooth structures such as enamel, dentine, cementum and pulp. The severity of presentation also varies depending on the strength of the

impact force and its vector⁵. Some cases may present as vertical crown root fracture, oblique crown-root fracture or with multiple crown-root fractures. Success of treatment of complicated crown-root fracture is generally based on the degree of impact of the trauma to the tooth supporting structures especially the periodontium, root-crown length ratio and extent and complexity of the fracture. There are few treatment options available in treating complicated crown root fractures:^{33, 34}.

- Removal of the fractured coronal fragment and restoration of tooth if the fracture line has not encroached into the biologic width
- Removal of the coronal fragment and supplemented with gingivectomy and osteotomy to expose the fracture in order to establish biologic width prior to restoration
- Removal of the coronal fragment and initiation of endodontic treatment and restoration of tooth with post crown
- Removal of the coronal fragment and initiation of endodontic treatment and later by orthodontic or surgical extrusion of the apical fragment prior to restoration with post crown.
- In severe crown-root fracture, the tooth may have to be extracted and replaced with removal or fixed prosthesis.

The extrusion rate used in this case was similar to that recommended by other authors^{16,17,26,35}. If the extrusion speed is too high, temporary stabilization is needed. According to recent studies, the force of 30–60 g is required to extrude the tooth^{17,20,21,23,26}. While other authors reported that forces of 70–150 g were necessary,²¹ in our case the initial force of 60 g did not move the traumatized incisor. The extrusion was possible at 120 g. The application of a large force has been reported to possibly cause pulp inflammation, root resorption, or a bone and periodontal loss, which did not occur in this case.

An orthodontic extrusion of fractured tooth will maintain the periodontal tissue at the same level and restore a physiological attachment. A 3–4mm distance from the alveolar crest to the coronal extension of the remaining tooth structure has been recommended for the optimal periodontal health.³⁶ This treatment is preferred over crown lengthening which moves alveolar bone and may become the reason for pocket formation. The orthodontic procedure allows the movement of fracture line supragingivally and then optimizes the

marginal sealing. The forced eruption was limited to 3 mm (it should be maximum 5 mm as suggested by Ingle)³⁷ and was achieved with minimal force (only 0.2-0.3 N).³⁶

The major limitation of this treatment is the longer duration of treatment and a longer stabilization period. It may also impair good esthetic resolution because the cervical diameter of extruded tooth is similar to the adjacent teeth.³⁸

Finally, the use of a goldern post with composite build up and porcelain jacket crown gives good esthetic result and increases retention and distributes the stresses along the root.³⁹

Conclusion

Restoration of traumatized teeth requires a close collaboration between different dental fields to avoid loss of tooth. Even though orthodontic extrusion reduces crown/root ratio and widens the embrasure, this approach allows to maintain the biologic width and optimizes the marginal sealing.³⁹

The present case reports a multidisciplinary management of dental trauma that leads to conservation of tooth and its permanent restoration. In addition, the adjacent teeth need not be prepared for fixed prosthesis and the alveolar bone is conserved.

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A review and critical analysis about dental phobia

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Abstract

Many dentally fearful people will only seek dental care when they have a dental emergency, such as a toothache or dental abscess. People who are very fearful of dental care often experience a "cycle of avoidance," in which they avoid dental care due to fear until they experience a dental emergency requiring invasive treatment, which can reinforce their fear of dentistry. Sometimes, one of the biggest challenges that a dentist has is when a patient with a phobia cannot necessarily articulate where their fear comes from. This makes the phobia more difficult to understand and manage, and is often the case when the phobia is based around a long-distant childhood memory. The patient does not necessarily need to be conscious of the memory for it to influence their behavior as an adult. The first step was to understand the fear and to identify the problem. During a full consultation with the dentist, he/she will identify the primary symptoms as anxiety, stress and fear and spent time with the dentist to try to understand what triggers them. The aim of the present article to review of dental phobia related articles. There is therefore a need to develop culturally sensitive instruments which would enhance the objective assessment of treatment need and treatment outcomes of dental fear in patient. Such instruments would help in effectively determining the efficacy of various treatment modalities for dental phobia in adults as well as children.

Key Words: Dental phobia, dental anxiety.

Introduction:

Dental fear or dental phobia has continued to generate a lot of interest in general dentistry. This is because of the handicapping complications associated with it. For one, it causes stress for many dentists who have to manage such patient especially those who have associated behavioral problems. In addition, chair time required managing and some specialized training is also needed for the effective management of this patients¹. Dental anxiety shares similar characteristics with many clinical anxiety disorders, and this is especially the case with other specific fears and phobias. These often debilitating conditions comprise several different dimensions, including cognitive, emotional, behavioral

and physiological components. In addition, dental anxiety and fear are associated with a range of aversive health consequences². The reasons people fear attending the dentist are varied and include pain, cost of treatment, lack of control while in the dental chair, embarrassment and fear of the unknown. The cause of dental anxiety is usually a previous bad experience, but can be caused indirectly through horror stories about dental treatment from family, friends and even the media. What do you fear most about going to the dentist? Just the thought of having a needle inserted into your cheek and a cavity removed from your tooth is enough to bring tears to the eyes. However, surprisingly it is not the actual dental procedure that most often terrifies patients. According to surveys, the site of a needle and the sound of the drill were the two most feared elements of dentistry. However, to effectively manage of this type of patient, it is important to determine the prevalence of problems in a community so as help in planning of public health services. There is also some physiological factor related with dental pain that may sometime create some extra stress to patient. Because of the oral cavity's proximity to the brain, as well as the complex nerve structure of the head and neck, dental pain is often more severe than pain in other parts of the body. One of the most troublesome biological factors that dentists must deal with is bacterial infection. In addition to the sensitivity caused

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by infections, the initial inability of oral infections in the teeth and bony structures to drain results in the buildup of pressure. As bacteria quickly multiply and produces gaseous toxins, pressure increases and pain results. If an infection is neglected for even a day or two, the pressure can become intolerable. Direct experience is the most common way people develop dental fears. Most people report that their dental fear began after a traumatic, difficult, and/or painful dental experience³. However, painful or traumatic dental experiences alone do not explain why people develop dental phobia. The perceived manner of the dentist is an important variable. Dentists who were considered "impersonal", "uncaring", "uninterested" or "cold" were found to result in high dental fear in students, even in the absence of painful experiences, whereas some students who had had painful experiences failed to develop dental fear if they perceived their dentist as caring and warm⁴.

A search and review of publications related to various identification tools used for assessing in dental phobia was done. Attention was paid to the findings with the main focus being the function for which instrument were designed. The features as an ideal instrument for use in the measurement of dental phobia were examined.

Discussion:

A controlled study of 34 patients with dental phobia was carried out to explore predisposing and etiological factors of phobia of dentistry. Dental trauma was found to be the most important etiological factor in dental phobia and two such experiences distinctly separated the two groups. Other predisposing factors are

discussed as well as the length of time between the last dental treatment and inclusion in this study, duration and intensity of pain and pain threshold⁵. A study was carried out among 79 patients in United States of America presenting for emergency extraction rated their anxiety and pain before, during, and two weeks after the procedure. Measures of trait dental anxiety and fear of pain also were collected. All patients exaggerated their recall of procedure pain, but only those high in trait dental anxiety exaggerated their recall of anxiety. Highly anxious patients reported more pain prior to the procedure and expected more pain; ratings of anxiety and pain for all participants assimilated over time⁶. A study was carried out in Denmark to obtain information about a group of young drug addicts' dental habits, knowledge, and attitudes. An improvement in the dental behavior in this group and a decrease in their dental disease is undoubtedly closely connected with stopping drug abuse, or at least reducing it, together with an improvement in these individuals' entire situation⁷. A study was carried out to find out prevalence of dental anxiety and the association between dental anxiety and personality in a population-based sample of 895 US urban children, from 5 to 11 years of age, from low-income families. Dental anxiety was reported by the child using the Dental Subscale (DS) of the Children's Fear Survey Schedule, and behavioral problems and personality traits were evaluated by parent report on the Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL). Mean DS scores were 31.1 (SD = 10.3) for boys and 34.3 (SD = 11.0) for girls. CBCL score means were 33.3 (SD = 23.2) for boys and 28.5 (SD = 19.1) for girls⁸. 75% of US adults experience some degree of dental fear, from mild to severe⁹⁻¹¹. Approximately 5 to 10 percent of U.S. adults are considered to experience dental phobia; that is, they are so fearful of receiving dental treatment that they avoid dental care at all costs¹². Between 45-55% of patients who attended the dentist are anxious in the dental environment. The reasons people fear attending the dentist are varied and include pain, cost of treatment, lack of control while in the dental chair, embarrassment and fear of the unknown. The cause of dental anxiety is usually a previous bad experience, but can be caused indirectly through horror stories about dental treatment from family, friends and even the media. What do you fear most about going to the dentist? Just the thought of having a needle inserted into your cheek and a cavity removed from your tooth is enough to bring tears to the eyes. However, surprisingly it is not the actual dental procedure that most often terrifies patients. According to surveys, the site of a needle and the sound of the drill were the two most feared elements of dentistry¹³⁻¹⁴.

Management:

When you make the appointment to see the dentist, tell the receptionist you are nervous about treatment. This first appointment will usually be to discuss your fears about treatment and to do an initial examination of your teeth¹⁵.

Behavior Management: This is the simplest method of treatment for nervous patients. It involves a careful and sympathetic approach from the dentist, with explanations of what is being done and allowing the patient control over the procedure. Some patients may want to bring a friend along for support. It may also be possible to play relaxing music or to watch a video while having treatment¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Dental Health Maintenance: Of course, the most important way to reduce the pain involved in maintaining oral health is by focusing on preventive care instead of the treatment of problems. If you've put off going to the dentist for years and have neglected regular flossing or brushing, you may be experiencing advanced stages of tooth decay or gum disease - both painful problems. The further decay spreads the more radical the treatment required. This causes trauma to the tooth and gums that results in discomfort¹⁹⁻²⁰.

New Advances in Dentistry

Dentistry has come a long way over the last few years and many of you will be surprised on your next visit. Even if you have put off going to the dentist and are experiencing problems, your dentist has new ways to provide relatively painless treatment. For invasive procedures such as wisdom teeth extraction, biopsies and complex root canal surgery, nerve block is often administered. This involves the injection of an anesthetic to block sensation to the nerve that sends pain signals to the brain. By blocking the nerve with an anesthetic, the dentist can numb the area requiring treatment for a specific period of time. To eliminate the discomfort associated with injections, topical agents are applied to tissues prior to the injection a soothing atmosphere and calm, reassuring dentist can make your next dental visit more pleasant²¹⁻²³.

Conclusion:

The various existing measures for assessing different aspects of dental fear have served various research purposes. However, their uses as measures to determine

treatment need and treatment outcomes are limited. There is therefore a need to develop culturally sensitive instruments which would enhance the objective assessment of treatment need and treatment outcomes of dental fear in children. Such instruments would help in effectively determining the efficacy of various treatment modalities for dental phobia in adults as well as children. The final part of a possible solution could be counseling, therapy or hypnosis, conducted by a certified professional. This should only be applicable to patients suffering from a deep-seated dental phobia. In the majority of cases, the starting points of patients would be to speak to their dentist, rather than a doctor. As dental phobias become more widely understood, more and more dentists are becoming familiar with how to treat them effectively

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Tooth-size Discrepancy – An important diagnostic tool to measure the outcome of Orthodontic Treatment Completion: A Review

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Abstract:

Final finishing occlusion of an Orthodontic treated patient often become challenging due to presence of pretreatment tooth tissue discrepancy (TDS). Earlier proper diagnosis of Tooth tissue discrepancy and planned the treatment accordingly will minimize this problem to a great extent. This article emphasis's the significance, methods of screening of tooth size discrepancies and previous study references upon this topic in national and international context.

Introduction:

A tooth-size discrepancy (TSD) is defined as a disproportion among the mesio-distal widths of maxillary and mandibular teeth of individual¹. Orthodontic treatment comprises different phases, and each segment presents unique characteristics and challenges. The orthodontic “finishing” phase is recognized for the multitude of details necessary to achieve an excellent result. In some cases, the finishing phase is very difficult, requiring the production of complicated biomechanical forces to reach a satisfactory orthodontic solution.

If a patient has a significant tooth size discrepancy (TSD) between the arches, orthodontic alignment of the teeth into ideal occlusion may not be possible². In order to achieve a good occlusion with the correct overbite and over-jet, the maxillary and mandibular teeth must be proportional in size. The mesio-distal widths of teeth were first formally investigated by G.V. Black³ in 1902.

He measured a large number of human teeth and set up tables of mean dimensions, which are still used as references today.

Many authors studied tooth width in relation to occlusion following Black's investigation. The best known study of tooth-size disharmony in relation to treatment of malocclusion was by Bolton⁴ in 1958. He evaluated 55 cases with excellent occlusions. Bolton developed two ratios for estimating TSD by measuring the summed mesio-distal (MD) widths of the mandibular anterior teeth to the corresponding maxillary anterior teeth.

Bolton concluded that these ratios should be 2 of the tools used in orthodontic diagnosis, allowing the orthodontist to gain insight into the functional and aesthetic outcome of a given case without the use of a diagnostic setup. In a subsequent paper⁵, Bolton expanded on the clinical application of his tooth size analysis. Bolton's standard deviations from his original sample have been used to determine the need for reduction of tooth tissue by inter-dental stripping or the addition of tooth tissue by restorative techniques.

Smith et al.⁶ stated that specific dimension relationships must exist between the maxillary and mandibular teeth to ensure proper inter-digitations, overbite and overjet. Within certain limits, this would seem self-evident. But still among orthodontists, opinions vary widely concerning the frequency of significant TSD and the need to measure it in clinical practice.

This review therefore aims:

- To evaluate the different methods of measurement of TDS and their significance on finishing of Orthodontic Treatment.
- To evaluate the different study those measure the TDS in different population.
- To evaluate the different study those measure the TDS in our Bangladeshi population.

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Significance of measuring TDS:

Without the proper mesio-distal tooth size ratio between the maxillary and mandibular teeth, correct coordination of arches would be difficult⁷ Tooth size discrepancies is an often overlooked problem in retention⁸.

Ballard⁹ reported that 90% of the casts of 500 patients he examined had tooth size discrepancies. When the maxillary anterior teeth are too large in relation to the mandibular anterior teeth, clinical manifestations may be one of the several problems, such as: (1) deep overbite (2) greater overjet, or (3) combinations of greater overbite and overjet, (4) crowded anterior segment or (5) out of proper occlusion buccal segment. On the other hand, if the mandibular anterior teeth are too large in relation to the maxillary teeth, compensations on tooth positions include, (a) end to end relationship of teeth (b) spacing in the maxillary anterior segment (c) mandibular incisor crowding and (d) improper occlusion of posterior teeth¹⁰.

Methods of Measuring TDS:

Bolton⁴ describe the formula to calculate the tooth size discrepancies between upper and lower teeth will be calculated as below

$$= \left[\frac{\text{sum of mesio-distal width of mandibular six anterior teeth}}{\text{sum of mesiodistal width of maxillary six anterior teeth}} \right] \times 100\%.$$

And to calculate the overall tooth size discrepancies between upper and lower teeth, he⁴ proposed the formula will be as below

$$= \left[\frac{\text{sum of mesio-distal width of mandibular twelve anterior teeth}}{\text{sum of mesiodistal width of maxillary twelve anterior teeth}} \right] \times 100\%.$$

To compute the data into the above formula, first the mesio-distal diameter of anterior six teeth (four incisors and two canines) and anterior twelve teeth (four incisors, two canines, four premolars and two first molar) on each jaw need to measure and then calculated through the above formula.

The traditional methods of measuring mesio-distal widths of teeth on dental casts can be described as manual methods and have either employed needle-pointed dividers or a Boley gauge (Venire calipers). Recent technological advances have allowed the introduction of digital calipers, which can be linked to computers for rapid calculation of the anterior and posterior ratios and the required correction to produce Bolton's mean ratio. Alternatively, digitized or scanned

images of the study casts can be measured on-screen. Ho and Freer¹¹ proposed that the use of digital calipers with direct input into the computer program can virtually eliminate measurement transfer and calculation errors, compared with analysis that requires dividers, rulers and calculators, although the same measurement error may be associated with the positioning of the calipers on the teeth. Zilberman *et al.*¹² also compared the measurement using digital calipers with OrthoCAD. Measurement with digital calipers produced the most accurate and reproducible results, but these were not much improved relative to the results with OrthoCad. Digital calipers seem to be a more suitable instrument for scientific work, but OrthoCAD's accuracy was considered clinically acceptable. Arkutu¹³ evaluated commonly used means of assessing a Bolton's discrepancy to the gold standard, which was defined as the measurement with a Venire caliper to 0.1 mm.

Tooth-size Discrepancy (TDS) in other population in Different Study:

The prevalence of tooth-size discrepancies (TSD) in the general population has been quoted as being 5% by recommended literature². However, the basis for this figure was not explained and it appears to be defined as the proportion of cases that will fall outside 2 standard deviations from Bolton's mean ratios.⁵ Recent studies conducted by Gerard *et al.*¹⁴ in 2010 among Irish population 37.9% had a clinically significant mean anterior TSD, which is higher than the recorded 17.4% in a British orthodontic population in 2007 by Orthoman SA¹⁵. However, Crosby and Alexander¹⁶ reported that 22.9% of subjects had an anterior ratio with a significant deviation from Bolton's mean (greater than 2 of Bolton's standard deviations). This is clearly a much higher figure than Proffit's recommended 5% prevalence of tooth-size discrepancies (TDS). They also noted that there were a greater percentage of patients with anterior TSD than patients with such discrepancies in the overall ratio. These findings are common to many investigations. In the study conducted by Freeman *et al.*¹⁷ it is noted that the overall discrepancy was equally likely to be relative excess in the maxilla or the mandible, whereas the anterior discrepancy was nearly twice as likely to be a relative mandibular excess (19.7%) than a relative maxillary excess (10.8%). Santoro¹⁸ and Souki¹⁹ found similar prevalence values to Freeman.¹⁷ Bernabe *et al.*²⁰ studied TSD in 200 Peruvian adolescents with untreated occlusions. Importantly, this sample was selected from a school, not

from an orthodontic clinic, so may not have been representative of patients undergoing orthodontic treatment.

Tooth-size Discrepancy (TDS) in Bangladeshi population in Different Study:

A few of such type of study was conducted in our country that is not sufficient enough to establish a country norm or representing the whole population. However among those studies Rahman²¹ found the mean value for anterior ratio was 79.4% with standard deviation ($\pm$)2.31% and the mean value for man was 79.29% with standard deviation ($\pm$)2.58%. In other studies by Ali²² the overall mean value was 79.34% with standard deviation ($\pm$)3.58%. These studies shows some idea regarding tooth tissue discrepancies (TDS) in our population, but things should be remember that those populations subjected to this study are only the patients attending the Orthodontic department of that hospital, not the country representing sample population.

Conclusion:

In sum up, we conclude that every orthodontic pretreatment model should go through this tooth tissue analysis before starting a orthodontic treatment to increase the success rate of final finish with whatever instrument and material is available on that circumstances. And further study upon this tropic in our population should be carried out to establish a country norm. Hope enthusiastic young learner and orthodontist will facilitated the study further.

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Changes in Residual Alveolar Ridge Following Tooth Extraction & the Necessity of Placing Bone Graft Material in the Extracted Socket to Prevent Bone Resorption - A Review Article

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Abstract:

Alveolar bone resorption is frequently observed after tooth extraction. Preservation of alveolar dimensions after tooth extraction is crucial to achieve optimal esthetic and functional prosthodontic results. Attempts to reduce alveolar bone resorption have included atraumatic extraction, the placement of natural roots, root analogues, and immediate implants into the extraction socket, sometimes in combination with membrane or graft techniques. This article reviews the literature on healing of the alveolus and its dimensional changes after tooth extraction, and discusses socket preservation techniques that have been introduced to minimize these dimensional changes.

Keywords: alveolar ridge resorption, bone graft, tooth extraction, healing of extracted socket, pattern of ridge resorption.

Introduction:

Alveolar bone seems to play a key role in providing support to the teeth, which are anchored to the bone by periodontal fibers. The progressive alveolar bone resorption process occurs due to a loss of anatomic, biologic and mechanical factors. Mechanical stimulation of alveolar bone during mastication is crucial in keeping the teeth and underlying bone healthy.

Loss of alveolar bone may be attributed to a variety of factors, such as endodontic pathology, periodontitis, facial trauma and aggressive maneuvers during extractions. Thousands of teeth are still extracted annually in Bangladesh. Most extractions are done with no regard for maintaining the alveolar ridge.¹

Tooth extraction and subsequent healing of the socket commonly result in osseous deformities of the alveolar ridge, including reduced height and reduced width of the residual ridge. The severity of the healing pattern may pose a problem for the clinician to place prosthesis like a dental implant.

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When tooth extraction is necessary, trauma should be minimized during the procedure and bone preservation should receive careful attention. The literature has shown that early bone loss can be significantly reduced by socket grafting. The process of socket grafting requires an understanding of wound healing and an appreciation of the biological properties of the products available for socket grafting.^{2,3}

Healing of extracted socket

The first stage of healing is the formation of clot or coagulum. The socket fills with blood from the severed vessels, which contain proteins and damaged cells. These cells initiate a series of events that will lead to the formation of a fibrin network, which, along with platelets, forms a "blood clot" within the first 24 hours. Platelet retract the clot, expressing fluid so that it becomes harder & shrinks below the level of soft tissues, pulling any mobile soft tissue inwards to reduce the area of the clot exposed. Lysis of clot begins within two days caused by fibrinolytic enzyme plasmin. At day 4, capillaries & fibroblasts (granulation tissues) are growing into the blood clot from the periphery so that it is now fixed to the socket wall. Epithelium at the gingival margin undergoes hyperplasia & starts to grow over the intact clot. By 4-6 weeks, most parts of the alveolus are filled with woven bone, while the soft tissue becomes keratinized. The mineral tissue within the original socket is reinforced with layers of lamellar bone that is deposited on the previously formed woven bone. Although bone deposition in the socket will

continue for several months, it will not reach the coronal bone level of the neighboring teeth.^{4,5,6,7}

Rate & Pattern of ridge resorption

The rate of resorption is most rapid in the first 2 years after extraction & can be as high as 4.5mm/year. Rate varies from 0.4mm/year to 2.9mm/year with an average of 1.36mm/year.

The resorption pattern is different in maxilla & mandible. The residual alveolar ridge resorbs downward & outward in mandible, whereas in maxilla resorption is upwards & inwards. As a result after several years maxilla becomes progressively smaller, whereas mandibular arch becomes wider. So there is a tendency of developing class III ridge relationship.⁸

Alveolar bone resorption and socket repair involve a complex cascade of events. Likewise, any successful ridge preservation technique is likely to have multiple mechanisms of action. Based on the current understanding of bone-implant interactions, several key concepts emerge for consideration.⁹

Alveolar ridge preservation technique and grafting materials

Alveolar ridge preservation (ARP) is a guided bone regeneration (GBR) application at the time of tooth extraction to control bone resorption. ARP is indicated after extractions to preserve original ridge dimensions and contours (hard and soft tissues), when immediate implant placement is not possible.¹⁰

The techniques for alveolar ridge preservation were introduced in the 1980s using hydroxyapatite in the form of root-shaped cones.^{11,12}

Current methods to prevent ridge resorption include the use of particulate alloplasts, xenografts, autografts, allografts, and membranes manufactured from various materials, including those that are bioabsorbable or non-resorbable, naturally derived or synthetic. Most of these materials have been shown to be osteoconductive, providing a scaffold for the osteoblasts to migrate and form bone.^{13,14,15}

Keys to successful extraction-socket grafting

According to Dr. Carl Misch, founder of the Misch International Implant Institute and one of the world's leading implantologists, some keys to successful bone grafting of extraction sites include:¹⁶

1. Atraumatic tooth removal;
2. An evaluation of the remaining walls of bone following the extraction, and evaluation of the size of the defect;
3. Asepsis and complete removal of granulomatous tissue;
4. Ensuring adequate blood supply to the graft site;
5. Graft containment and soft tissue closure;
6. Choice of an appropriate graft material;
7. Ensuring adequate time for healing.

Conclusion

Disuse atrophy of the alveolar ridge post-extraction is preventable through the use of grafts or implants. Grafts provide viable future options in cases where an implant is not an immediate option. Prosthodontic results are substantially improved and bone mass may be preserved for the subsequent placement of dental implants. Further studies are needed to evaluate the long-term effects of ridge preservation materials and to develop standardized protocols for their use.

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INVITATION

Dear Dental Surgeons,

'Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International' (BADI) is the national honor society for dental professionals dedicated to sharing knowledge in order to serve the dental-health needs and to improve the quality of life of people throughout Bangladesh.

Convened by Dr. Md. Jahangir Kabir (President, BADI) & Dr. Chowdhury Moin Jan (General Secretary, BADI), we will be organizing the celebration of the **Golden Jubilee of Bangladesh Dentistry** and '**South Asian Dental Congress & Int. Dental Trade Fair**' on **5th, 6th & 7th January 2012** at BIAM auditorium, Eskaton, Dhaka.

There will be Scientific seminars, Hands-on-courses, Rally, Dental Trade Fair & Cultural shows. Promising new dental interventions will be presented by eminent speakers & latest techniques will be simulated by expert professionals on Scientific seminars & Hands-on-courses. Leading manufacturers & exporters of dental equipments & materials will represent their latest innovations & future ideas throughout the trade fair.

Your cordial co-operation is expected & relevant contribution will be highly appreciated.

With Thanks

Dr. Md. Jahangir Kabir
President

Dr. Chowdhury Moin Jan
General Secretary

Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International (BADI)

E-mail : info@badi-bd.org, Website : www.badi-bd.org

ANNOUNCEMENT

'Bangladesh Academy of Dentistry International' (BADI) is going to organize **Continuous Dental Education Program (CDEP)** From the beginning of February 2012 at CDEP Centre, BADI, 140-141 Shantinagar, Al-Amin Tower- 3, Dhaka 1217. CDEP is a 3 months course which includes 28 classes with Hands-on-course with live surgery on Dental Implant, Minor Oral Surgery, Orthodontics, Prosthodontics, Endodontics, Preventive Dentistry & Use of Laser Dentistry. These courses will be conducted by renowned professional experts.

For more information; contact:

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